

Ayırım turmıs tárizi salamat emes shańaraqlarda hayalǵa bolǵan zorlıq nátiyjesinde onıń múmkinshilikler sheńberi sheklenedi, perzentler tárbiyasında unamsız jaǵdaylar júz beriwi múmkin. Hayaldıń shańaraqtaǵı ornı bekkem bolsa, jámiyettegi poziciyasi joqarı boladı. Házirgi kúnde hayallar mámleket sektorlarında, mámleketlik emes shólkemlerinde iskerlik alıp barıp jámiyettegi gúlleniwine úlken ules qosıp kelmekter. Hayallar áwele ana hám shańaraq biykesi bolıp tabıladı. Shańaraq bolsa jámiyetiniń tiykarı bolıp tabıladı. Jámiyette jámiyetlik aktiv bolǵan hayal shańaraqta da óz orınına iye boladı jámiyet ómiriniń belgili bir tarawda iskerlik kórsetiw ushın hayal joqarı bilimli hám mánawiyatlı bolıwı kerek. Hayallardıń sociallasıwı olardıń zamanagóylesiwi hám shıdamlılıǵı menen joqarı dárejede jetilistiriwip baradı. Hayal jámiyetteb ǵana emes shańaraqta da ibratlı úlgige aylanadı. Onıń shańaraqta perzent tárbiyalaw sıyaqlı áhmiyetli wazıypalardı orınlaw processinde hayal (jámıyet talapların jaqsı túsinip jetedi hám perzentlerinde) ózindegi barlıq etikalıq hám mánawiy táreplerin perzentlerine sińiredi. Jámiyetlik aktiv hayal bilimli bolǵanı ushın perzentlerinen ziyreklilik, zeyinlilik páziyletlerin tárbiyalaydı. Jámiyet ómirinde belsene qatnasta bolǵan hayal jámiyet talapların jaqsı túsinip jetedi hám perzentlerinde uqıplılıq, isbilermenlik iskerligin qalıplestiredi. Jámiyettegi siyasiy ómirinde júz berip atırǵan ózgerislerdi jaqsı túsinip jetken belsene hayal perzentlerinde siyasiy hám ekonomikalıq ómirde belsene qatnasta bolıw ózgesheligin qalıplestiredi. Ol tárbiya processinde sadıqlılıq, turaqlılıq, bir sózlilik hám jámiyettegi barlıq waqıya hádiyselerge óziniń ǵárezsiz pikirin bildire alıwı, mánawiy dúnya qarası joqarı bolǵan shaxstı tárbiyalaydı. Jámiyette jámiyetlik aktiv bolǵan hayal óz perzentlerin búgingi kún múmkinshiliklerine ǵana emes, bálki ertengi kún mıtájliklerine súylene otirip tárbiyalaydı. Hayal-qızlar elimizdegi ózgerisler processinde belsene qatnasıwı menen birge, óziniń bilimi professional ilimiy tájiriyesi menen jetekshi poziciyalardı iyelep kelmekkte. Búgingi kúnde ómirimizde úlken orın alıp atırǵan fermerlik háreketi, kishi biznes hám jeke isbilermenlikti, ilim-pán, medicina, talim-tárbiya, mádeniyat hám kórkem óner sıyaqlı áhmiyetli taraw hám tarmaqlar rawajlanıwın hayallardıń qatnasıwısız hátteki oyımızǵa da keltire almaymız.

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CONVERSION IN PRESENT-DAY ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article explores the linguistic phenomenon of conversion, or zero derivation, in present-day English. Conversion allows a word to shift from one grammatical category to another without morphological changes, demonstrating the language's inherent flexibility. The article examines the mechanisms behind noun-to-verb, verb-to-noun, adjective-to-verb, and adjective-to-noun conversions, providing contemporary examples for each type. The implications of conversion for linguistic economy, context-dependence, and the productivity of English are discussed. This study highlights how conversion contributes to the dynamic evolution of the English language, enhancing its expressive and communicative potential.

Key Words: Conversion, Zero derivation, Linguistic flexibility, Noun-to-verb, Verb-to-noun, Adjective-to-verb, Adjective-to-noun, English language evolution, Morphology, Syntax.

Introduction. Conversion, also known as zero derivation, is a process in linguistics where a word changes its part of speech without any morphological alteration. This phenomenon is particularly prevalent in English due to its relatively flexible word order and minimal inflectional morphology. This article examines the mechanisms of conversion, provides examples from contemporary English, and discusses the implications of this process for language users.

Mechanisms of Conversion. Conversion involves the functional shift of a word from one grammatical category to another without adding a suffix or prefix. Common types of conversion include noun-to-verb, verb-to-noun, adjective-to-verb, and adjective-to-noun conversions.

1. **Noun-to-Verb Conversion:** This is one of the most common types of conversion. For example, the noun "email" has been converted into the verb "to email."

- Example: "I'll email you the details."

2. **Verb-to-Noun Conversion:** Verbs can be used as nouns with no change in form. For instance, "to run" (verb) can become "a run" (noun).

- Example: "She went for a run this morning."

3. **Adjective-to-Verb Conversion:** Adjectives can be converted into verbs, though this is less common. An example is "to clean" from the adjective "clean."

- Example: "We need to clean the house."

4. **Adjective-to-Noun Conversion:** Adjectives can function as nouns, often with a change in meaning or context. For example, "the poor" uses the adjective "poor" as a noun.

- Example: "We must help the poor."

Examples of Conversion in Present-Day English:

To illustrate the phenomenon of conversion, here are some examples from modern English usage:

1. **Text (Noun to Verb)**

- Noun: "I received a text from her."

- Verb: "She texted me the address."

2. Google (Proper Noun to Verb)

- Proper Noun: "Google is a popular search engine."

- Verb: "I googled the information."

3. Impact (Noun to Verb)

- Noun: "The impact of the decision was significant."

- Verb: "The new policy will impact the company's operations."

4. Highlight (Noun to Verb)

- Noun: "The highlight of the show was the finale."

- Verb: "She highlighted the key points in the document."

Linguistic Implications:

The process of conversion reflects the dynamic nature of the English language. It highlights several important linguistic characteristics:

1. Economy of Language: Conversion allows for linguistic economy by enabling the use of existing words in new grammatical roles without the need for additional morphemes.

2. Context-Dependence: The meaning of converted words often depends heavily on context, showcasing the importance of pragmatic understanding in language use.

3. Productivity: The productivity of conversion demonstrates the flexibility and adaptability of English, allowing it to incorporate new usages and meanings rapidly.

Conclusion: Conversion is a significant linguistic phenomenon in present-day English, showcasing the language's flexibility and capacity for innovation. By examining the mechanisms and examples of conversion, we can better understand how English evolves to meet the communicative needs of its users. This process not only enriches the language but also enhances its expressive potential.

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